

CRISIS MANAGEMENT IN PRIVATE HIGHER INSTITUTIONS: EXPLORING LEADERSHIP PRACTICES FOR BUILDING RESILIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Private higher education institutions in the Philippines have faced numerous crises around the world—natural disasters, pandemic, and even internal crises. These disruptions have revealed weaknesses and questioned the sustainability of private higher education institutions, particularly in crisis-prone areas like Kalibo, Aklan. This study seeks to reveal the leadership practices demonstrated by educational leaders for building resilience in the context of crisis management in their institutions. Qualitative research method was used in the study, particularly the case study method to gather an in-depth analysis of the individual cases of these private institutions. A semi-structured interview guide was utilized to gather data. Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis was used to analyze these data and identify potential themes. Three core themes emerged—(1) Crisis to Opportunities, which identifies the type of crises that educational institutions have experienced composing of natural disasters, health crisis, and manpower crisis, and the opportunities that emerged with it; (2) Crisis Increases Dynamism, which elaborates the educational leader's dynamic problem-solving strategies as response to crisis including crisis management structures, risk assessments, resource management, stakeholder management, and innovative education; (3) Crisis Begets Resilience, which emphasizes the leadership styles of educational leaders that evolved during crisis—adaptive, transformational, and collaborative. The resulting output—the 'Resilient Leader' Framework aims to provide institutions guidance for building a more crises-resilient institutional community. This study adds to a broader discussion educational leadership and emphasizes the importance of strategic foresight, adaptability, and inclusiveness in navigating the ever-evolving landscape of private higher education institutions.

Keywords: *Crisis management, Private institutions, Building resilience, Adaptive Leadership, Digital infrastructure, Risk Assessment*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the frequent and severe impacts of crises have grown globally, therefore affecting the educational landscape. These include several types of crises ranging from natural disasters, socioeconomic and technological challenges, and even health crises. This complex and rapid growth of the global risk landscape is raising concerns from all throughout the world (*World Economic Forum, 2023*). With this being mentioned, schools have adapted in response to various crises to keep the quality of education and the welfare of their stakeholders (UNESCO, 2020). These statements made clear how crucial it is for educational institutions to have robust and effective crisis management procedures—therefore, effective educational leadership is necessary to overcome these challenges and maintain institutional sustainability (Bowers, Hall, & Srinivasan, 2017).

Educational institutions in the Philippines have not been exempted from these difficulties. Because of the nation's vulnerability to typhoons and earthquakes as well as its socioeconomic problems, effective crisis management strategies are crucial (World Bank Group, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic brought even more attention to how important it is for educators to have resilient and flexible leaders. Both public and private educational institutions have had to put a variety of crisis management techniques into place to ensure the safety and well-being of their faculty, staff, and students while upholding their strict standards of instruction (Chatzipanagiotou & Katsurou, 2023).

However, private institutions which are self-sufficient and only get limited support from the government under certain conditions are at a greater risk when managing numerous crisis signals. In a report by Inquirer.net in August 2022, the Department of Education has announced that 425 private schools in the Philippines have permanently closed since 2020, which only proves how severe the impact of the unforeseen challenges were. These closures were due to the pandemic that recently turned the educational institutions upside down. This rising number of closures emphasizes the vulnerability of private institutions in times of crisis. These circumstances do not only affect the education of learners but the community as a whole, including the socioeconomic stability of the locale they are located.

In 2020 alone, five private schools in Aklan, specifically in Kalibo, New Washington, and Malay had shut their operations down due to low enrolment caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (*Panay News*, 2020). Adhering to the local context, Kalibo, Aklan, where a number of private higher education institutions reside, institutions have encountered a distinct array of challenges. In the present, there is limited guidelines and studies on how educational institutions sustain their operations despite going through crises. Gaining an understanding of these procedures is crucial to improving institutions' ability to manage crises in the future.

Despite the importance of crisis management in institutions, studies focusing on building institutional resilience is limited. Studies that have been conducted have given a focus on public institutions, offering generic solutions that neglect the unique characteristics and needs of private institutions. The closure of 425 private schools in the country highlights the need for deeper research on institutional resilience and stability challenges and strategies. Therefore, this gap highlights the need for focused research on how private education institutions thrive through crisis and build resilient school communities.

Philosophical Assumptions

According to Johnson and Clark (2006), researchers must be conscious of the philosophical decisions they make when selecting a research strategy since these decisions will influence the work they conduct and the way they interpret the subject of their investigation. Creswell (2013) noted that five philosophical assumptions lead to an individual's choice of qualitative research: ontology, epistemology, axiology, methodological, and rhetorical assumptions. These assumptions will be utilized and further discussed in the context of the role of leadership in sustainable crisis management.

Ontology

In the context of this study, ontology refers to the meaning of reality which is constructed by individual experiences and interactions. This implies that in the context of crisis management in private higher institutions in Kalibo, Aklan, the strategies, interventions, and practices employed by school leaders are not objective, instead, subjective. Their actions are shaped by their different perspectives, experiences, and cultural contexts. This study viewed the way school leaders utilized strategies and practices in building resilience and managing crises in their institutions based on what they have experienced, and who they are, and what they think is fitting upon the situation. There is no one "right" way to manage crises; rather, the realities of each leader's institution and personal life influence their approach, which makes crisis management techniques more varied and context specific.

Epistemology

In this context, the researcher acknowledges that the knowledge about crisis management and leadership practices are constructed through the perspectives and experiences of the educational leaders in the private higher education institutions in Kalibo, Aklan. The strategies applied are not universally applicable, because it depends on the specific challenges faced by each institution. The study aimed to explore how these institutions' leaders interpret their experiences during times of crisis. Through investigating their various viewpoints and insights, the study sought to comprehend the several ways in which people cultivate and implement resilience-enhancing strategies. The emphasis is on understanding these leaders' distinct realities and realizing how their local surroundings and the particular situations they face poses a significant impact on their knowledge and methods.

Axiology

The axiology of this study laid on the researcher's values and the emphasis given to resilience, sustainability, and transformational leadership in the context of educational crisis management and understanding how these values are incorporated into leadership practices in private higher education institutions in Kalibo, Aklan. It recognized that the selection of research questions, the analysis of the data, and the suggestions given are all influenced by the researcher's personal opinions about the importance of these principles. Thus, the study is motivated by the idea that crisis management in education requires robust and sustainable leadership. This value informs the researcher's method, which focuses on identifying practices that adhere to these principles. The research is driven by a commitment to promote leadership that fosters sustainability and resilience in educational communities, not just the collection of data.

Methodology

This study used a qualitative approach and focused on exploring leadership practices of educational leaders in the context of crisis management at private higher education institutions in Kalibo, Aklan. The study used interviews and thematic analysis to collect in-depth information from educational leaders in research locales. This method considered particular difficulties and situations these leaders encountered, enabling a thorough analysis of how these leaders created and put plans into practice to strengthen resilience inside their organizations. This study

collects experiences and narratives directly from these private institutions' leaders through interviews. This attempts to analyze the interventions and practices they employed in handling crises and assist their school communities by examining these narratives. Qualitative method is employed to better convey the depth and complexity of their leadership practices.

Rhetoric

In order to effectively communicate the intricate and context-specific leadership techniques in crisis management inside private higher institutions in Kalibo, Aklan, this study used descriptive and narrative rhetoric. To emphasize the real-world experiences and crisis management techniques of educational leaders, the language used is reflective. In order to engage readers and provide insights into the processes of resilience-building within educational communities, more particularly in private higher education institutions, the study presented its findings in a way that highlights the nuances and intricacies of leadership in these difficult situations. This paper used a storytelling method to describe the actual experiences of educational leaders in handling crises. The wording is thoughtful and unambiguous, with the goal of illuminating how these leaders strived to maintain the strength of their institutions. The approach emphasized the human aspect of crisis management in education by making the findings relatable and clear.

Domain of Inquiry

This study aimed to focus on the leadership practices employed by educational leaders in managing crisis and building community resilience in schools in Kalibo, Aklan in the year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What were the experiences of educational leaders during crisis?
2. What is the essence of these experiences and how were they able to manage the crisis?
3. What framework can be formulated or crafted based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology used in the study, including the research design, participants and environment, sampling techniques, data gathering tools and procedures, data analysis, and ethical considerations observed throughout the research process.

Design

This study employed qualitative research design. According to Moser & Korstjens (2017), qualitative research investigates and offers a more profound understanding of real-world problems. The case study approach is utilized in the study. The objective of a case study is to acquire as much information as possible about an individual or group to generalize the findings (Cherr, 2024). This approach is chosen as it will provide an in-depth analysis on the leadership practices employed by educational leaders of private higher education institutions in Kalibo, Aklan, in the building resilient school communities and in managing crises.

This approach examined private higher education institutions as individual cases, acknowledging the uniqueness of each institution's context. This will also allow the researcher to identify themes that can generate broader conclusions on crisis managements in similar contexts.

Participants and Environment

The participants of this study included eight (8) educational leaders, such as administrators, presidents, quality assurance officers, crisis management officers, and program heads from private higher education institutions in Kalibo, Aklan, who have been in their current leadership roles since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic (March 2020 onwards). These participants have played a significant role in crisis management during the pandemic and actively contributed to strategies and decisions that impacted their institutions' resilience and continuity. Additionally, these leaders were affiliated with institutions that have been continuously operating for at least five years, providing stable context for the investigation of sustained crisis management practices. This includes five out of six private higher education institutions - Aklan Polytechnic College, Northwestern Visayan Colleges, Saint Gabriel College, Aklan Catholic College, and STI College.

Conversely, individuals who assumed their leadership positions after the COVID-19 pandemic began or who lacked direct involvement in crisis management during this period were excluded. Furthermore, participants from institutions with less than five years of operational history, or those who do not hold a leadership or decision-making role, were also not included. This approach ensures that the study focused on experienced leaders who have

directly influenced their institutions' responses to crises, providing rich insights into the practices that build resilient school communities.

Sampling technique

The sampling technique used is purposive sampling, adhering to the criteria for the selection of participants which consists of educational leaders who have experienced and held a key role during the pandemic and have been in their current position from 2020-2022.

Data Gathering Tools

Data were collected through a semi-structured interview questionnaire with eligible participants. Since the study is exploratory in nature, this data gathering tool is most appropriate. Semi-structured interviews allowed flexibility to ask follow-up questions and to collect comparable and reliable data (George, 2022).

The semi-structured interview questions were designed to explore the educational leaders' experiences, perceptions, and practices in the context of managing crises and building resilience in their school community. This allowed the researcher to gather in-depth information about the topic of interest, and also allowing participants give additional insights that the researcher might not have anticipated.

Data Gathering Procedures

Pre-Data Gathering. The researcher complied with all the necessary requirements and protocols imposed by the University REC before proceeding with data gathering. A permit to conduct the study was addressed to the Dean of the UV Graduate and got approved. Succeeding to approval, a letter of permission to conduct the study was addressed to each private higher education institution and potential participants containing the objectives and purpose of the study and request their participation.

Actual Data Gathering. When the consent was obtained, the interviews were scheduled based on the time and place which was convenient for the participant. During the interview, the participant's responses were recorded with consent. The researcher began asking general questions and gradually moved on to more specific questions about the participants' experiences and leadership practices and strategies on crisis management. In addition to audio recording, the researcher also took notes of the insights, non-verbal cues, and other aspects that were relevant to the exploration of the subject. Each interview lasted for an hour or less, but not more than the requested time.

Post Data Gathering. Confidentiality and privacy of participant information are rigorously maintained, with data anonymization applied to protect individuals' identities and sensitive data. The data gathered were secured and only the researcher had access to the participant's data. After the results have been obtained, all handwritten and printed notes and transcriptions were shredded. As to digital and audio data, these were permanently deleted on the flash drives where they were saved.

Data Analysis

The data recorded were transcribed verbatim to maintain an unbiased and detailed record of the interviews conducted. These transcripts were reviewed thoroughly for completeness and accuracy. Further, these were subjected to inductive thematic analysis. According to Riger and Sigurvinsdottir (2016), thematic analysis is a method for analyzing qualitative data that involves recurring ideas or themes. Braun and Clarke (2006) developed six phases of thematic analysis, and this was utilized in the study. In the execution of the first phase, the researcher familiarized the data transcribed. These were then coded to identify patterns and themes in association to leadership practices for crisis management. Data were analyzed per institution; responses were first coded individually, then consolidated and compared across schools to identify common themes and unique contextual insights. These codes were examined to identify initial patterns and categorize them into broader patterns that emerged as potential themes. Afterwards, these were reviewed to ensure that they actually represent the data and proceeded onto naming these themes and ensured that each name encapsulates the data it represents. To finalize the process, these themes were combined in a narrative that will discuss the findings and their significance in relation to the broader literature of leadership practices in the context of crisis management.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. It has been approved following the protocol of the Research and Ethics Committee of the University of the Visayas with Reference No. 2025-083 dated April 21, 2024. The research involved adults participating voluntarily in an interview. Before participating in the interviews, an accompanying cover letter explained the confidentiality and purpose of the study, the potential objectives, and the voluntary participation. No financial incentives were provided for participating in the study. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study focused on identifying key themes related to the crises experienced by private higher education institutions in Kalibo, Aklan, their responses, and the lessons they learned. Each major theme is supported by sub-themes, highlighting various facets of institutional experiences throughout institutional crises.

Table 1. Characterization of Participants

No.	Pseudonym	Position	Years in Current Position	Years in Educational Leadership
1	Jarren	School President	9 years	9 years
2	Michael	School President	6 years	12 years
3	Ralph	Associate Director for Quality Assurance	12 years	36 years
4	Josh	School Director	15 years	22 years
5	Mika	Quality Assurance Director	9 years	9 years
6	Klang	Program Head	7 years	15 years
7	Will	Quality Management Representative	7 years	17 years
8	Fyang	School Administrator	6 years	7 years

The participants in the study were composed of eight educational leaders, all of whom were holding prominent roles in decision making. They were school presidents, school director, quality assurance director, and program head, who has gained 6 to 15 years of experience in their current position, and an overall experience in educational leadership spanning from 7 to 36 years, which indicates a well-balanced group, as it represents a wide variation of insights from long and middle experienced leaders.

This wide variety of inclusions offers a rich dataset which gives perspectives that bridge academic, strategic, and operational domains. Further, this provides strong evidence of their authority and expertise in managing crises in the field of educational management. These implications will best discuss their experiences during crises, the essence of these experiences, and how they managed the situation.

Emerging Themes

This section presents the experiences of educational leaders during crisis as described in their own words, through thematic analysis. Three major themes emerged upon the consolidation of the participants' responses to opportunities, crises increase dynamism, and crises beget resilience. The first theme highlights the types of crises institutions have faced and what opportunities came with it. The second theme introduces the interventions and strategies that educational leaders employed in the midst of responding to crisis and how they prepare for potential crises. The third theme underscores the leadership styles that the participants have executed in the face of crisis management. These themes are further discussed thoroughly in the succeeding narratives.

Theme 1. Crises to Opportunities

Sub-theme 1.1. Natural Disasters

Natural disasters significantly affect school communities, putting safety at risk, threatening well-being, and influencing educational achievement (*The School Services Sourcebook*, 2024). These bring with them a wide variety of unique problems and coping challenges.

Natural disasters affected around four billion people worldwide between 2000 and 2019, with an estimated \$2.97 trillion in economic damages (*UnD.E.S.A.*, 2022). Higher education institutions have not been exempted from these disruptions because they are crucial components of the social infrastructure. Numerous investigations have demonstrated that academic activities have been disrupted and there have been material and financial losses (Baytiyeh H., n.d.). In the context of this study, natural disasters were reported by educational leaders as a type of crisis their institutions have faced.

"Apat na bagyo na ata ang dumaan sa amin, pero yung pinaka-matindi talaga si Typhoon Frank. Nasira yung 57 na computers namin kasi yung library at mga opisina noon nasa ground floor pa." (There were around three typhoons that hit us, but the worst was Typhoon Frank.

The water rose really high—around 57 computer units got damaged because the offices and the library were still located downstairs at that time.) – Ralph

"Mostly natural disasters tulad ng bagyo at flooding, lalo na tuwing rainy season." (Mostly natural disasters such as typhoon and flooding, especially during rainy seasons.) – Michael

"I remember, Typhoon Ursula, 2018 or something like that, grabe to iya. Nag-adto ako sa school the next day. Ang daming nasira na infrastructures and facilities. Naduea man kato ro kuryente it pilang adlaw." (I remember Typhoon Ursula; it happened in 2018 or something like that. I visited the school the next day and there were so many infrastructures and facilities that were damaged. There was no electricity for a long time during that period.) – Jarren

This affirms a study by Shimada (2022), that dictates natural catastrophes that cause serious infrastructure damage and socioeconomic disruptions, endangering the security and functionality of educational institutions. In this sense, displacement of students happens preventing them from physically taking classes and participating in in-person education. Moreover, school closures frequently become an option (Buchana, et al., 2022).

This implies that these disruptions not only threaten the continuity of academic programs but also poses a major hindrance to an institution's stability as these private higher education institutions often rely on income which comes from student fees to sustain their usual operations. Financial strains may result from these prolonged closures and displacements, forcing institutions to implement extreme measures, such as reduce staffs, compromise expenditures in facilities, and in worst case scenarios – permanent closure.

This highlights the need of integrating crisis management plans into educational policies and institutional governance to ensure resilience amidst future calamities.

Sub-theme 1.2. Health Crises

In 2020, the world was struck by a world-wide health emergency declared by the World Health Organization – the COVID-19 pandemic and much has been written about the situations ever since. And this sudden onset posed an unprecedented disruption to all educational institutions, particularly in the context of private HEIs, and this was echoed by all participants.

"One of the biggest challenges we faced as a private higher education institution during crises, particularly at the height of the pandemic, was how to sustain operations and ensure students could continue their education despite disruptions." – Jarren

"During the pandemic, our main challenge was how to continue providing our services. At first, we were at a loss." – Josh

"Noong March 2020, biglaan ang announcement ng lockdown. Wala kaming nakahandang learning platform that time." (Last March 2020, the lockdown announcement was too sudden. We did not prepare any learning platform that time.) – Michael

This implies that there were significant challenges that also emerged during the pandemic. The fact that these educational institutions struggled to maintain their regular operations indicates their level of uncertainty, lack of preparedness and the need for their immediate action and response. This supports the findings of Zhang et al. (2020), who contended that the pandemic exacerbated pre-existing educational disparities and necessitated quick pedagogical innovation. Since school communities found themselves thrust into an emergency mode of operation in inevitable chaos, its emergence "an unprecedented test for organizations around the world" and has significantly challenged the educational framework (Chatzipanagiotou & Katsarou, 2023). The pandemic, unlike natural disasters which are time-bound, brought upon a systemic and prolonged disruption in every aspect of educational institutions – enrollment, institutional governance, curriculum delivery and pedagogy. With this, school administrators received a great deal of expertise as crisis management actors during this process.

"Through continuous consultation, planning, and guidance from government regulatory agencies, we developed solutions to prepare for flexible learning. One of the most vital decisions we made was to be the first in the area to implement flexible learning for our students. We also initiated preventive measures to ensure the continuity of our services." – Josh

"No'ng pandemic, operational pa rin naman kami. Pero naging challenge talaga yung bayad sa tuition. Pero naka-adjust kami agad—gumawa kami ng modules, online enrolment, tapos 'yong bayad pwede na through GCash or Palawan. At least tuloy-tuloy pa rin yung learning ng students." (By the time of the pandemic, we were still operational. However, the collection of the tuition fees became a challenge. But we immediately adjusted – we prepared modules, online enrolment, and payments of tuition was made easier through GCash or Palawan. At least the learning of students continued.) – Ralph

"Sa learning ng students, we initially looked for ways to continue teaching despite the restrictions due to COVID. We consulted with CHED on what they would allow and based our approach on their guidelines. We explored different methods: online learning, distance learning, modular learning, rotation learning, and one-on-one sessions where teachers would visit students. We also considered sending materials via mail. Our strategy depended on what students could and couldn't do." (On the part of student learning, we initially looked for ways to continue teaching despite the restrictions due to COVID. We consulted with CHED on what they would allow and based our approach on their guidelines. We explored different methods: online learning, distance learning, modular learning, rotation learning, and one-on-one sessions where teachers would visit students. We also considered sending materials via mail. Our strategy depended on what students could and couldn't do.) - Jarren

"We immediately formed a crisis task force and shifted to remote learning using basic tools like Google Classroom and Facebook Messenger." - Michael

These responses prove that the pandemic became a catalyst for digital transformation. The worldwide educational system had undergone a significant change, with an emphasis on the necessity of digital transformation, as traditional in-person instruction gives way to online learning (Mhlanga & Moloi, 2020). The situation forced educational institutions to rethink and invest in digital solutions – an implication that the pandemic shifted these educational institutions to become resilient, innovative, and technologically-enabled. Additionally, more than institutional resilience, educational leaders' creativity and commitment were evaluated as they went beyond what is being done and ensured every learner will have the opportunity to continue their studies. Operational stability was not the only goal – educational equity was visibly existent.

Subtheme 1.3. Manpower Crises

Participants described the rising crisis of faculty turnover, particularly from private to public HEIs. In addition to individual resignations, this problem is characterized by a sustained pattern of departures that threaten institutional stability and instructional continuity. This teacher turnover intention has drawn extra attention from practitioners in several decades already. This is because it is a factor of disrupting organizational conduciveness (Alifuddin & Widodo, 2021). The responses present repetitive emergences of sudden and steady departure of educators, which is a common internal crisis in the private HEIs.

"Yong isa pa palang risk na nakita namin ay yung exodus ng mga teachers from private institutions papunta sa public schools." (Another risk we saw was the exodus of teachers from private to public schools.) – Mika

"Aside from the pandemic, another crisis we experienced and still experiencing ay 'yong consistent resignation ng mga teachers. Most of them left for better-paying jobs abroad or transferred to public schools for more stability." (Aside from the pandemic, another we experienced and still experiencing is the consistent resignation of our teachers. Most of them left for better-paying jobs abroad or transferred to public schools for more stability.) - Klang

These emphasize the vulnerability of private HEIs to workforce loss compared to government-regulated HEIs, which offers much-competitive salaries, benefits, stability. According to Mulkeen & Crowe-Taft (2010), teacher turnover is critical to low-to-middle income countries has been a critical issue in where salary differentials, job security, and career mobility often entice teachers away from private institutions. These problems contribute to a wide variety of implications for the organization. Employee turnover allegedly leads to a decrease in productivity (Park et al., 2021) and employee performance (Lin & Huang, 2020), given that it is directly proportional to organizational effectiveness (Ahmed et al., 2016) and organizational performance (Lai & Chen, 2012).

Turnover intention has emerged as a crucial idea in the twenty-first century for overseeing employee career advancement and business continuity at all levels, particularly in the service sector (Hassan & Jagirani, 2019). It implies that an organization's management will often endure if they can lower the likelihood of turnover. Given this, institutions must consider their strategies for crisis preparedness the retention of faculties as a critical component.

"...so, ang ginagawa namin, pag may nagde-demo na teacher, sinasabi na agad namin na may lock-in clause sa contract nila na kailangan nilang mag-stay for 3 to 5 years. Binibigay naman namin lahat—training, benefits—pero hindi muna sila pwedeng mag-resign agad." (...so, what we do is, when there are applicants doing their teaching demonstration, we immediately inform them that we have a lock-in contracts which states that they'd need to stay in the institution for at least 3 to 5 years. We actually give them everything—training, benefits—for the condition that they won't be able to resign yet during a specified period) - Mika.

"We had to reassign loads, hire part-timers, and conduct crash training sessions para mapunan ang kakulangan. Nag-focus kami sa internal capacity building habang naghahanap ng sustainable na solusyon." (We had to reassign loads, hire part-timers, and conduct crash training to fill the gap. We focused on capacity building while finding a sustainable solution.)

– Klang

"We chose to promote promising junior faculty into full-time roles kaysa kumuha agad sa labas. It gave them purpose and helped fill the gap after senior teachers left." (We chose to promote promising junior faculty into full-time roles than to hire from the outside. It gave them purpose and helped fill the gap after senior teachers left.) – Klang

As coping mechanisms, these responses indicate attempts which are capacity building and adaptive human resource strategies. Since the migration of teachers from these private higher education institutions affects not only the capacity of the institution to deliver instructions but forces the remaining teachers to carry heavier workloads therefore affecting performance and morale (Ingersoll and Strong (2011), educational leaders in this context, responded by enforcing contractual obligations, providing trainings, and promoting from within.

"May teacher wellness program kami, retention incentives, at leadership training para sa mga next-in-line sa administration." (We have teacher wellness programs, retention incentives, and leadership training for those who are next-in-line in the administration.) – Klang

This demonstrates an institution's proactive approach to the crisis identified. Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2017), noted that the main causes of teacher departure are financial insecurity, burnout, and lack of career advancement, in which wellness programs and retention incentives attempts to address these. Further, succession planning is reflected in junior faculty leadership training, which facilitates easier transitions and inspires employees by outlining clear career paths.

Theme 2: Crisis Increases Dynamism

Subtheme 2.1. Crisis Management

Unexpected events can occur inside or outside of institutions at any time and can refer to a variety of dimensions or elements, such as the type of event, the time and location of its occurrence, its frequency, and its duration. With this, institutions need to be able to manage all of these unexpected manifestations in order to thrive in unpredictable circumstances and promote future success (Duchek, 2020).

One recurring strategy that was existent was the creation of crisis management teams in which institutions assign particular people to oversee the short-term and long-term responses.

"...meron kaming tinatawag na crisis committee, and every personnel has their own task..."

(...we have what we call the crisis committee, and every personnel has their own task...) – Will

"May naka-assign na rin na Crisis Response Officer sa admin team." (A Crisis Response Officer is also assigned to the admin team) – Michael.

"Bale may na-assign na committee para i-inform ang management at ma-troubleshoot yung mga aspects na related sa crisis." (A committee has been assigned to inform the management and troubleshoot aspects related to the crisis.) – Mika

This depicts the institutions' preparedness in times of crisis, allowing them to respond timely and effectively because the designated personnel know their role and attends to it.

"If this happens, ano gagawin? ...something like that, and then yung risk plan, ginawa siya ng Core Team [Crisis Management Team]" (If this happens, what will be done? ...Something like that, and then the risk plan was created by the Core Team [Crisis Management Team].) – Mika

In this response, the team facilitated decision-making by making sure that there are personnel assigned to identifying a potential crisis and a corresponding course of action as response. Creating crisis management teams as a proactive action ensures resilience as it helps institutions assess and strategize before crises actually happen and therefore being prepared.

According to Debeş (2021), the school crisis team determines how effective crisis management in institutions is. Crisis management frameworks, according to Boin and van Eeten (2013), improve an institution's agility by enabling rapid information processing and action. Further highlighted by Kenney and Gormley (2020), crisis officers or teams assist educational institutions in better coordinating emergency responses, preventing bottlenecks brought on by ambiguous hierarchies. Thus, these private higher education institutions institutionalized resilience by proactively establishing crisis teams and clearly defining roles, guaranteeing that processes, not just individuals, could sustain the organization during times of disturbance.

Subtheme 2.2. Risk Management

Participants also highlighted the crucial role of conducting regular and strategic risk assessments as a practice for building institutional resilience. Instead of being reactive, educational leaders emphasized the necessity for identifying potential risks and therefore producing strategies for mitigation even before it actually leads to disruption.

"...so, may mga ano din may mga, 'if this happens, ano gagawin?'" (...So, we also have, 'if this happens, what will be done?') – Mika

"Well, ang crisis management sa institution namin ay more on reducing the impact ng crisis base sa mga risks na nakita na namin beforehand—so more on mitigation talaga. May template kami: may risk ID, then yung mismong risk na identified namin, tapos kino-categorize namin kung moderate ba siya, high-risk, o low-risk lang." (Well, crisis management in our institution is focused more on reducing the impact of a crisis based on the risks we identified beforehand—so it's really more on mitigation. We have a template: it includes a risk ID, then the specific risk we identified, and we categorize it as moderate, high-risk, or low risk.) – Mika

This implies that the institution has already adapted a template for this strategy of risk assessment. Further, they categorize crises according to their potential impact, making the allocation of resources and efforts for intervention prioritized accordingly.

"We now conduct regular risk assessments." - Klang

"Now, because of certain things nga nakikita namon in the world, gabalik euman kami sa planning—mga resiliency planning, mga contingency planning, strategy planning. So, we need to do that again." (Now, because of certain things that we see in the world, we go back to planning—resiliency planning, contingency planning, strategy planning. So, we do that again.) – Jarren

Aside from regular conduct, institutions review their contingency, and resiliency plans in response to new threats since risk assessment procedures are dynamic and changing. Being proactive in crisis management entails foreseeing interruptions and formulating plans to lessen their effects. Smith & Elliott (2020) underline the benefits of scenario preparation and preparedness, enabling organizations to swiftly react to unforeseen obstacles. This proactive strategy minimizes disruptions to teaching, research, and student engagement while ensuring that institutions of higher learning are better prepared to handle emergencies (Thanitbenjasith & Kamkankaew, 2023).

"Ga-research pa kami kato, so we have that sort of awareness of the world. Hamakon mo, may giyera kita sa China. May gano'n na kami—bukon kami it buki." (We did research at that time; so, we have that sort of awareness of the world. Imagine, an ongoing war with China. We already foresee that—we are not ignorant.) – Jarren

"Kailangan natin mag-prepare for economic concerns in the future because of the trade war in the US, issues with China. Things will be expensive, so we need to be more self-reliant, meaning, uwa kita ga-depend sa guwa." (We need to prepare for economic concerns in the future because of the trade war in the US and issues with China. Things will become more expensive, so we need to be more self-reliant, meaning, we can't depend on external sources.) – Jarren

This response also exhibits that leaders must not only respond to visible threats but must also anticipate future ones—future thinking. In the context of higher education, future thinking is essential for efficient crisis management because it entails imagining potential outcomes, emerging trends, and preparing for unforeseen circumstances (Thanitbenjasith & Kamkankaew, 2023).

By embedding risk awareness into proactive crisis management, institutions surpass beyond short-term response mechanisms and contribute toward a more sustainable and resilient educational community.

Subtheme 2.3. Resource Management

Another emerging sub-theme is the recurrence of the importance of resources—both human and financial—as an indispensable aspect of building institutional resilience.

"Honestly, it's about money. Why? Money represents resources, and in a crisis, you need resources." – Jarren

This response underscores the value of financial resources for operational continuity in institutions. This reiterates that education financing has a direct impact on every aspect of education as there are costs associated with things like building and equipping schools, teaching supplies, compensating faculty, technology, everything related to delivering educational services (Akyüz et al., 2023). The institution's development and students' progress are directly tied to funding (Plessis, 2020; Chikoko and Mthembu, 2020).

Moreover, it is undeniable that crises, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic, challenged institutions without financial reserves. Globally, the COVID-19 epidemic had a negative effect on educational systems, causing financial crisis that led to permanent closures (Debnath, 2024).

"For us, we made sure to pay our teachers for six months, even without classes. I told them, "Kahit umabot pa tayo ng 1 year na walang pasok, kaya ko kayong swelduhan." – Jarren

This shows how the institution pays attention to the importance of human resources and therefore provides support to them throughout the disruptions caused by the crisis. According to Afebia (2016), institutional personnel in low-income countries have left for better opportunities due to inadequate and unappealing incentive packages and other service conditions. This suggests that educational leaders utilize financial resources to support human resources for their retention and loyalty, and boost their morale and productivity, especially in times of crisis. Research has also shown that motivated employees are more likely to engage in their tasks (Van Beek et al., 2012).

For efficient school administration, educational leaders must invest in human resource management—hire faculties, build strong connections with them, invest in their training and development, keep them on board, and have them compensated (Kyereh et al., 2023). As a result, its significance cannot be minimized. Further, in a literature review by Edvardsson and Durst (2021), "soft" human resource management is the best practice in times of crisis that poses threat to the health and well-being of employees—taking care of employees through training, social and psychological rewards, support, and motivation. This fosters an environment of dedication and trust (Bearwell & Clark, 2010).

"Hayun, may pera ka, you train your people. Resources mo are cash and people. Why do you need cash? Kailangan mong bumili ng generator, kailangan mong mag-install ng madaming electric fan—kailangan mo ng cash. Why do you need people? Because you need people to implement these, you need people to team up strategies." (There, you have money, you train your people. Your resources are cash and people. Why do you need cash? You need to buy a generator, you need to install many electric fans—you need cash. Why do you need people? Because you need people to implement these, you need people to work together on strategies.) – Jarren

This emphasizes the financial and human resources are indispensable aspects of crisis management. It cannot be denied that financial resources have a direct impact on every aspect of education (Akyüz et al., 2023). Additionally, investing in teachers is particularly needed so that they are prepared for the challenges that crises may cause (Vargas, 2021). This statement also reinforces the role of investing in human resources, so they become effective actors in the crisis management process—assessing, strategizing, and deciding.

*"May updated contingency plans na..." (We already have updated contingency plans...) – Klang
"Lagi kaming nagse-set aside ng contingency fund para in case na mangyari ito..." (We always set aside contingency funds, so, in case this happens...) – Mika*

These proactive response highlights institutions' preparedness for unforeseen events that may hamper their institutional operations. Emergency resources are formally allocated for enhancing institutional resilience. In the event of unexpected problems or catastrophes, a well-managed contingency fund permits rapid and effective response (*Contingency Funds: What Are They and How Much Should You Set Aside? - Multiproject, 2024*).

"Mas proactive na rin ang training programs ng faculty." (The faculty trainings were already proactive.) – Klang

In the context of participating institutions, investing in human resources signifies the school's commitment in empowering their administrative and academic staff and preparing them for immediate transitions that may occur. According to a study by Johnson et al. (2019), continuous professional development programs that stress skills related to the future, like scenario planning and creative pedagogies, enable teachers to deal more effectively with uncertainty.

"May mga commercial rentals din kaming pinagkukuhaan ng pondo, tulad sa kabilang campus na may pinarentahan." (They also generate funds from commercial rentals, like in the other campus where they have spaces for lease.) – Ralph

"We engaged in business... Kaya nga, ginagawa namin na may cash kami and may iba pang negosyo, para kung may mangyari sa amin, hindi namin mawawala 'yong mga mabubuting tao namin." (We engaged in business... That's why we make sure we have cash and other sources of income, so that if something happens to us, we won't lose our good people.) – Jarren

These responses highlight the educational leaders' perception regarding the value of financial resources to sustain other resources. Alternative financial sources such as going into business resonate with the participants' innovative thinking to ensure that the institution will not rely merely on the budget derived from their students' tuition fees and other basic institutional income. To ensure that their institutions thrive in spite of challenging times, they invested in aspects that will give the institution additional income to sustain and improve their services.

In conclusion, the integration of financial and people aspect as crucial components of crisis management is a holistic resilience approach. By focusing on these areas, institutions went beyond simply surviving and deliberately created operational buffers to withstand future crises.

Subtheme 2.4. Stakeholder Management

In the context of building institutional resilience, another major pattern among participating stood out—consultation and engagement with the right stakeholders.

Since higher education institutions are a part of broader ecosystems that comprise communities, industry partners, alumni, and students (Thanitbenjasith & Kamkankaew, 2023), crisis management requires thorough consultation with school personnel as well as reliance on both internal and external subject matter experts (Debnath, 2024). In managing crises, effective leadership is not defined by merely asking everyone and gathering their opinions; effective crisis management also entails identifying the right stakeholders and collaborating with them.

"But you need to choose the right stakeholders... Not all groups, even if they belong to the same category, are actually stakeholders. The first step is selecting the right stakeholders. During a crisis, you have to decide which stakeholders to involve." – Jarren

This implicates that not everyone affected must be actively involved—the quality of engagement matters more than the quantity of representation. Not being able to select the right stakeholders may impair the quality of decisions that may be made due to the high pressure it may imply. Bryson (2020) stated that determining who should be involved, how, and when to conduct is a crucial strategic decision.

"We consulted with CHED on what they would allow and based our approach on their guidelines." – Jarren

"We were instructed to do an alternative learning procedures, the guidelines are provided by the CHED." – Ralph

"...through continuous consultation, planning, and guidance from government regulatory agencies, we developed solutions to prepare for flexible learning." – Ralph.

"We do consultations particularly the parents as well as our faculty..." – Ralph

"We invite the faculty at staff sa planning sessions. Kahit student council—nakikiisa sa brainstorming at communication campaigns." (We invite the faculty and staff to the planning sessions. Even the student council participates in brainstorming and communication campaigns.) – Klang

In the engagement process, participating institutions exemplifies discernment in the selection of stakeholders. They had identified government agencies (Commission on Higher Education), selected student and parent groups, critical members of the faculty and staff, as key stakeholders. These consultations were active processes of negotiation, adaptation, and exchange of information in response to internal and external inputs, especially with relation to government regulations and health protocols.

"Talk to your team, talk to your academics, talk to your administrative staff, kasi sometimes yung mga crisis, yung mga maliit na isyu, galing sa mga tao." (Talk to your team, talk to your academics, talk to your administrative staff, because sometimes the crises, the small issues, come from the people.) – Fyang

This response underscores the importance of internal stakeholders in addressing issues that may emerge in any time concerning the institutional operations, which is in line with the leadership paradigm proposed by Spillane (2005), which views leadership as a shared practice embedded in interactions between leaders, followers, and the circumstances present. According to Leithwood et al. (2020), meaningful consultation with members improves change management outcomes.

Though these approaches were selective, they are still deemed to be inclusive for a reason that despite leaders gave priority to those who could actively engage, they still kept an open mind to opinions from all levels since they understood that participation was the foundation of trust and ownership.

Overall, these indicate that purposeful, strategic, and goal-driven consultations and engagements are necessary during times of crisis. If educational leaders will not be able to discern, the risk is poor and misguided decision making and arise. On the other hand, deliberate interaction with the right stakeholders enhances institutional agility, fortifies decision-making, and fosters a resilient, learning-oriented institutional culture.

Sub-theme 2.5. Innovative Education

A new reality has been brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has affected 1.6 billion students in over 190 countries. Additionally, 94% of the world's student population—up to 99% in low and lower-middle income

countries—has been impacted by the closure of schools and other learning facilities (UNESCO, 2020). Given this, institutions were forced to rethink how they can deliver basic functions; but some institutions already had strategies in place.

According to the participating educational leaders, two of the most important strategies for building resilience are investment in digital technology and capacity building for faculties. Participants underlined that institutions were better prepared to sustain operations and service continuity amid disruptions like the COVID-19 pandemic if they had proactively reinforced their technological systems and trained their faculties prior to the event.

"Siguro in our case, at that time, hindi na bago sa amin 'yong online learning because before 2020, I think...early 2016 or 2015, meron kaming tinatawag na ELMS or E-learning management system, so meron na agad na facility 'yong mga students where they can view their modules, where they can answer their activities, and so on... So, during the pandemic, it wasn't that much of an adjustment kasi naumpisahan na nila 'yon years back. Kasi this is already in place years ago, isa na yun sa mga backup na meron ang institution bago pa mangyari itong crisis na 'to." (Maybe in our case, at that time, online learning wasn't new to us because before 2020, I think... early 2016 or 2015, we already had what we call an ELMS or E-learning management system, so the students already had a facility where they could view their modules, answer their activities, and so on... So, during the pandemic, it wasn't that much of an adjustment because they had already started that years ago. Since this was already in place years ago, it was one of the backups the institution had before this crisis even happened.) – Fyang

This response demonstrates an educational leader's forward-thinking capability. This means that creation of proactive techniques that allow institutions to anticipate crises and take proactive steps to mitigate their effects is crucial (Thanitbenjasith & Kamkankaew, 2023). In recent years, educational systems around the world have prioritized their educational agendas to adapt strategies or policies around ICT integration (European Commission, 2019) and increased their investment in ICT integration (Fernández-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Lawrence & Tar, 2018). These technological advancements became an advantage when the pandemic struck as they were prepared.

"Gumawa kami ng online mental health support system; nag-develop din kami ng self-learning modules for low-connectivity areas..." (We created an online mental health support system; we also developed self-learning modules for low-connectivity areas...) - Michael

"One of the most vital decisions we made was to be the first in the area to implement flexible learning for our students." – Ralph

This highlights the institutions utilization of technology as response to the crisis, in order to sustain the institutional and academic operations. The pandemic became an opportunity for the world to adapt to digitization (Olaniran & Maphalala, 2020), simply because technological advancements paved the way to access teaching and learning, which was immensely demanded by the situation.

However, problems and difficulties emerge with this new learning approach. Since most of the teachers are products of the traditional learning environment (Bandalaria, 2020), the abrupt transition to digitization posed a major challenge for teachers as they encountered challenges when it came to planning and delivering lessons; faculty knowledge and proficiency in managing virtual learning environments surfaced.

"Nag-invest kami sa training ng faculty sa tech tools." (We invested in training the faculty on technological tools.) – Michael

"... train your people. ...Because you need people to implement these, you need people to team up strategies." – Jarren

These statements implicate that teachers must undergo training in order to deliver their tasks effectively. In a study by Dayagbil (2023), higher education institutions and their stakeholders need to be prepared to embrace the new reality in learning modalities in order to remain relevant and resilient after the pandemic, even in the absence of crisis. It is possible to rationalize faculty capacity trainings to concentrate on integrating students into the new standard of instruction and learning.

"We now have a digital learning management system. Meron na ring standing protocol for remote learning and work-from-home setups." (We now have a digital learning management system. We also have a standing protocol for remote learning and work-from-home setups.) – Michael

"Mas proactive na rin ang training programs ng faculty." (The faculty trainings were already proactive.) – Klang

These demonstrate that institutions started to institutionalize their reactive responses to the pandemic. Digital learning systems, remote learning, and work-from-home setups were already embedded into regular operations.

Dayagbil (2023) stated that by dealing with the health crisis, institutions implemented immediate solutions and plans in place to guarantee that teaching and learning continue. Given this, the pandemic became a breeding ground for innovations and strategic actions. Initiatives for long-term adaptation that foster organizational expansion have been clear and specific circumstances were taken into consideration while contextualizing these strategies according to the needs of the institution.

Theme 3. Crisis Begets Resilience

Subtheme 3.1. Adaptive Leadership

The extraordinary changes brought about by the pandemic ultimately challenged educational leaders. Unlike in the past, school leaders are currently being put to the test in new ways. School leaders cannot simply return to the educational leadership techniques they used during the earlier era of certainty, stillness, and predictability, as stated by Harris and Jones (2020). As school leaders, they can increase their school communities' resilience and ability to withstand future pandemic-related disruptions by embracing an adaptive leadership style (Bagwell, 2020).

"May tinatawag kaming 4Cs and one of those C's being Change-adapt, so with that parang nag-adapt tayo dun sa situation. Kasi the situation that time is already there, alam mo yun. Kasi di naman tayo mapigilan ng isang magic power or whatever, pero we adapted to the situation..." (We have what we call the 4Cs and one of those C's—being change-adapt. So, with that, we adapt with the situation since it's already there, you know... Because we cannot stop it by magic powers or whatever. So, we adapted to the situation.)

– Fyang

This response from a participant exhibits adaptive leadership. Since catastrophes and change are inevitable, being adaptive is key to withstanding the waves that come alongside. As defined in a study by Uhl-Bien et al. (2007), the term "adaptive leadership" describes the flexible, innovative, and educational behaviors that arise from system interactions as they attempt to adapt to stress (such as limitations or disturbances). This paradigm places a strong emphasis on learning while leading in uncertain times, modifying organizational procedures, and inspiring others to take on difficult tasks.

This type of leadership was demonstrated among the responses of the participants.

"We explored different methods... Our strategy depended on what students could and couldn't do." – Jarren

"Binago naming 'yong curriculum to be more flexible and responsive to the situation.'" (We changed the curriculum to be more flexible and responsive to the situation.) – Jarren

Instead of using a one-size-fits-all approach, the institution modified its teaching methodology according to the situation and abilities of each student, which is a sign of adaptability under pressure. This response reflects the study by Uhl-Bien (2007), on the responsive nature of leadership which contributes to the flexibility and learning of an institution amidst complexity. Adaptive leadership is a leadership behavior that arises from the fusion of various approaches that enable people to become more flexible and capable of making decisions and expressing themselves with awareness and understanding while striving for difficult changes, novel ideas, and new work adjustments in which institutions modify new work procedures to meet their goals (Chanchai et al., 2024).

"We immediately formed a crisis task force and shifted to remote learning..." – Michael

"We had to reassign loads, hire part-timers, and conduct crash training sessions para mapunan ang kakulangan." (We had to reassign loads, hire part-timers, and conduct crash trainings to fill the gaps.) – Klang

Reacting swiftly while also preparing the institution for sudden challenges in the future is the essence of adaptive leadership, which is reflected in these tactical yet reactive decisions. These responses demonstrate how these institutions effectively managed both the external threat posed by the crisis and internal issues. These educational leaders, who faced sudden head-on challenges, responded in real time to address immediate needs of the institution—changed policies, restructured workloads, and made an immediate training investment, which if not acted upon immediately, may disrupt the institutional operations.

Given the circumstances, adaptive leadership in institutions is entailed in planning for potential disruptions in addition to surviving a crisis. These educational leaders assessed the institution's ability to provide a customized crisis response, student limits, and technological availability. These procedures promoted operational continuity while emphasizing how important it is for educational leaders to be adaptable and creative.

3.2. Transformational Leadership

While adaptive leadership tackles urgent issues, transformational leadership seeks long-term change and institutional regeneration. Avolio et al. (1991) denoted that there are separate components of transformational leadership—idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. These leaders do not focus solely on crisis response—they go beyond. As defined by Bass (1985), they are leaders who inspire and motivate followers to go beyond expectations through personal growth, encouragement, and vision.

Crisis such as the COVID-19 highlighted the kind of world we are in – volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous. Institutions could no longer rely on their traditional day-to-day practices; instead, they need to stimulate their constituents towards their mission despite the adversities.

"Actually, 'yon ang trabaho ng Presidente. A President is supposed to be a person nga may strategic vision—nakikita mo yung malayo... So, kung talagang Presidente ka, malayo kang tumitingin, nasasagap mo yung information, marunong kang magsabi na "this is noise, this is important." (Actually, that's the job of a President. A President should be a person with strategic vision—someone who sees far ahead... So, if you're truly a President, you think long-term, you absorb information, and you know how to say, "this is noise and this is important.") – Jarren

This response embodies the idea that a leader's strategic foresight serves as guidance for their members. This reflects the characteristic of a transformational leader to inspire followers to actively participate in future-focused thinking and express optimistic expectations for required tasks (Bass & Riggio, 2006; Antonakis et al., 2003). Further, as highlighted by Bass & Riggio (2006), transformational leaders are excellent in distinguishing essential points from distraction, which is necessary for leaders to motivate their members in what to focus on to achieve their shared goal—helping members projecting that they have wisdom and can be depended on. They function as strong role models who are admired, respected, and trusted by their members – idealized influence.

"I-share ko lang sa COVID—may balita ata kami kato as early as December, there is this virus in Wuhan. Ga-research pa kami kato, so we have that sort of awareness of the world. Hamakon mo, may giyera kita sa China. May gano'n na kami—bukon kami it buki." (Let me share during COVID—we heard news as early as December about a virus in Wuhan. We were already doing research. So, we had that kind of global awareness. Imagine, we were already thinking about the war in China. We were not ignorant.) – Jarren

This fits Northouse (2019) definition of a transformative leader – a proactive individual who already prepares for courses of action even before it actually happens. Inspirational motivation, which is also one characteristic of transformational leadership, takes place when leaders motivate their members by providing them with challenges and meaning, projecting hope and optimism for the future, which in turn enables dedication to a common goal. And this is better translated when leaders do not only convey a compelling vision but through tangible actions – early preparation, clear communication, and consistent reinforcement of shared objectives.

"We used the pandemic as an opportunity to pause, reflect, and commit to delivering higher-quality education... Everything we did had accountability and clear deliverables." – Jarren

This highlights how innovation, critical reassessment, and reform was encouraged in spite of the crisis. Intellectual stimulation, the art of raising doubts about presumptions, challenging status quo, and encouraging people to consider exploring new possibilities; is evident in this response. It is a tremendous weapon in leadership that may unleash a team's potential, encouraging creativity and propelling expansion (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Instead of trying to survive, this institution created a culture of accountability and potential improvement, which gave faculty and staff a sense of hope, a shared purpose, and a sense of ownership. This implies that a transformational leader has the capacity to portray crises as a crucial trait for organizational excellence, strengthening both resilience and long-term institutional vision.

"I chose to promote promising junior faculty into full-time roles kaysa kumuha agad sa labas. It gave them purpose and helped fill the gap after senior teachers left." (I chose to promote promising junior faculty into full-time positions rather than immediately hiring externally. It gave them a sense of purpose and helped address the gap left by departing senior teachers.) – Klang

"During the time of sakuna, may bagyo, do you expect this person to be at school or to be at home? Kung sabat karon, "Sir, I expect this person to be here helping me out," i-reregular namin 'yan." (During times of disaster, like a typhoon, do you expect this person to be at school or at home? If your answer is, 'Sir, I expect this person to be here helping me out,' then we'll regularize them.) – Jarren

These inhibit decisions about leadership are based not only on the needs of the institution but also by identifying and developing dedication, character, and potential of members. These responses demonstrate individualized consideration—a leader who demonstrates this, displays awareness of the unique talents and abilities that each member contributes to the institution and helps them cultivate and exhibit these essential behaviors and skills. As a result, the follower exhibits inherent drive in their work and strives for future development (Towler, 2020).

Moreover, transformational leaders are always receptive to new ideas. They are always open to new ideas, regardless of where they may come from, and they are continuously searching for opportunities to do things differently.

"Actually, lumaki pa kami because of the pandemic. Mas tumaas pa ang income namin. Negosyante kami, and we do business with the heart for improving people." (Actually, we grew even more because of the pandemic. Our income increased. We are entrepreneurs, and we do business with a heart for improving people's lives.) – Jarren

This demonstrates how educational leaders not only adapt, but as well, thrive by aligning business success to a greater cause. This aligns with Bass's (1985) definition of a transformative leader, in which they cultivate a sense of collective purpose that goes beyond individual interests. This implies that the approach models ethical behavior, inspiring others to become committed not just for the sake of profits but for a much meaningful impact.

Further, According to Bass & Riggio (2006) and Northouse (2019), transformational leaders can turn risks into opportunities, inspiring the whole organization to come out stronger and more responsive. In this instance, continuous progress and development was not hampered by the COVID-19 crisis; instead, it improved organizational growth and dedication to the common good.

Overall, transformational leadership became a distinguishing tactic for educational leaders in the midst of managing crises. Their ability to see beyond the crisis, instill hope and trust, motivate others, and maintain dedication points to the lasting importance of transformative leadership in educational governance, particularly in private institutions that are facing existential challenges.

Subtheme 3.1. Collaborative Leadership

In the wake of the recent pandemic, collaborative leadership also surfaced as an approach usually practiced by educational leaders for surviving difficult times. Unlike transformative leadership which highlights empowerment and innovation, collaborative leadership focuses on transparency and inclusivity, which garners insights collectively.

The first step is selecting the right stakeholders. During a crisis, you have to decide which stakeholders to involve.

"It's important to engage with the right stakeholders—those who are willing to contribute. The challenge is in their engagement; if they don't open up, you might make the wrong decision by listening to them. The first step is selecting the right stakeholders. During a crisis, you have to decide which stakeholders to involve." – Jarren

This statement embodies a good application of collaborative leadership. One significant point of collaborative leadership is selecting the right stakeholders to be involved. This represents not the mere "inclusion" but a strategic and a more purposeful engagement with the stakeholders who will provide a meaningful input in decision-making. Bryson et al. (2006) indicated that finding and involving the right stakeholder is crucial in making sound and effective decisions especially at times of institutional crises.

"We created consultation groups composed of teachers, parents, and student reps." – Michael
"So, *pinatawag ng management lahat ng President, faculty, at staff para gumawa ng plano. Lahat involved — pati student organizations. Kaya nakagawa kami ng maraming pages ng plan...*" (So, the management called all the Presidents, faculty, and staff to create a plan. Everyone was involved — even student organizations. That's how we were able to come up with several pages of plans...) – Ralph

"We do consultations particularly the parents as well as our faculty, then when we have data..." – Josh

"Para aware sila and also makapagbigay ng feedback kung paano sila makakatulong." (So they would be aware and also be able to give feedback on how they could help.) – Mika

"We invite the faculty at staff sa planning sessions. Kahit student council—nakikiisa sa brainstorming at communication campaigns." (We invite the faculty and staff to the planning sessions. Even the student council joins in the brainstorming and communication campaigns.) – Klang

This leadership style indicates that educational leaders are not just applying it to seek advice, rather, it involves producing interventions, actions, and strategies, when collaborating with stakeholders whether internally or externally.

"Yong involvement ng ibang stakeholders is definitely malaking factor sa success kung ano mang implementation ang gagawin kasi sila din yung kumbaga sila din yung involved dito no so at that time, maraming consultations and meetings ang ginawa ng mga faculty members, employees, at that time, lahat ay parang hindi sigurado kung ano ang mangyayari." (The involvement of other stakeholders is definitely a big factor in the success of any implementation because they're also the ones involved in it. At that time, there were many consultations and meetings conducted by the faculty members and employees, and during that period, it felt like no one was really sure about what was going to happen.) – Fyang

Liu et al. (2022) emphasized that collaborative leadership allows institutions to customize their strategies that are responsive to the needs of their community, especially at times of crisis.

These findings correspond with Heifetz, Grashow, and Linzsky's (2009) notion of this type of leadership style, which highlights the need of involving stakeholders to develop solutions collaboratively amidst uncertainty and complexity, rather than depending on the top management themselves. Instead of perceiving stakeholders who are people that only accept the decisions made from the top, leaders see them as partners who are important in making important decisions.

"However, through continuous consultation, planning, and guidance from government regulatory agencies, we developed solutions to prepare for flexible learning." – Josh

"Also, talk to your team, talk to your academics, talk to your administrative staff, kasi sometimes yung mga crisis, yung mga maliit na isyu, galing sa mga tao. And when you know your people and your people know the clients they serve, they can better prepare for the school year or something." (Also, talk to your team, talk to your academics, talk to your administrative staff, because sometimes crises or small issues come from the people. And when you know your people and your

people know the clients they serve, they can better prepare for the school year or anything that comes.) – Fyang
These responses underscore the role of collaboration in addressing concerns that arise while managing crisis.

"It's also important to build relationships with agencies, with government offices para in the situation na kailangan natin ng form of assistance, pwede tayong mag reach out sa kanila." (It's also important to build relationships with agencies and government offices so that in situations where we need some form of assistance, we can reach out to them.) – Fyang

Collaboration also went beyond the school walls—educational leaders partnered with external stakeholders to strengthen the institutional response. Dubrin (2013), called this "networked leadership" in which leaders intentionally engage across sectors to improve the institution's capability to respond to crises more effectively.

In conclusion, collaborative leadership values transparency, inclusiveness, and quality. It is built on trust and accountability among stakeholders, and amongst all, it improved the quality of the decisions being made. Engaging stakeholders enabled institutions to leverage localized knowledge and logistical support, which were crucial to sustain operations in challenging times. Collaborative leadership emerged as a mindset among educational leaders in which there is an emphasis on supporting collective wisdom rather than an isolated authority.

In the context of crisis management within private higher education institutions, these three leadership styles have surfaced as unique, yet complementary strategies utilized by educational leaders. Transformational leadership was clear in the educational leaders' ability to plan for the future and how they motivate their members through a strong vision, renewed commitment, and encouragement of innovation. Meanwhile, adaptive leadership was present based on how a leader adjusts their strategies based on what is needed in a certain context, guiding members to lead despite vulnerability, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity. And lastly, collaborative leadership surfaced on the way leaders have involved stakeholders – from teachers to the community – to participate in decision-making, which will ensure inclusivity and the advantage of shared responsibility.

THE RESILIENT LEADER FRAMEWORK

The crisis, especially the pandemic in 2020, brought upon a tremendous challenge particularly in the context of private higher education institutions. With this, to maintain continuity, adaptation, and long-term sustainability in the face of the disruptions, these institutions have had to rethink their leadership and decision-making processes. This study investigated the ways in which educational leaders in private higher education institutions managed these crises, pinpointing the strategies, realizations, and institutional changes that helped them withstand and bounce back from these challenging times.

The 'Resilience Leader' Framework is created upon careful considerations of the findings. This framework captures the experiences, strategies, and leadership styles of educational leaders in the context of crisis management in private higher education institutions. Grounded in qualitative data, which was derived from the interviews with educational leaders, the framework is composed of three (3) major thematic domains: (1) Crises to Opportunities; (2) Crisis Increases Dynamism; and (3) Crisis Begets Resilience. Each theme signifies a progression—from experiences, to transformation, and to resilience.

Figure 1. 'The Resilient Leader' Framework

characterized by the occurrence of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the manpower crisis which signifies the unprecedented migrations of teachers from private to public institutions. Despite the challenges and hardships brought up by these crises, it created an opportunity for institutions to innovate and reform, and the most notable positive aspect is the digital transformation that emerged from the difficulties.

The second theme, crisis to dynamism, focused on how institutions responded to different sorts of crisis, showing dynamism. This included the interventions, actions, and strategies that educational leaders leveraged. Crisis management teams were established—composing individuals who are assigned with clear roles for the mobilization of organized and timely responses. This also included the institutionalization of formal crisis management protocols that institutions have adopted.

Another strategy complementing this is risk assessment; institutions who have remained resilient are those who have already prepared for crisis even before it happens. This includes the preparation of proactive plans, reviewing and upgrading these, categorizing them according to their severity, and planning corresponding courses of actions to be taken, in order to sustain their operations even in times of crisis. Resource management also emerged as a dynamic response, which involved strengthening human and financial resources. The institutions that were able to retain their staff, implement necessary interventions, and have contingency funds to weather the crises were the ones that survived and were able to sustain their operations. Leaders acknowledged that money is not merely a form of currency; it is the ability to take action and a crucial resource that will sustain other resources. Another pillar underscores the importance of consultation and engagement with the right stakeholders—stakeholder management. Engaging the stakeholders ensures a shared sense of ownership in navigating crises and provides depth to planning. However, it is crucial to distinguish the right stakeholder to guarantee that decision-making is informed by dialogue and rooted in the needs of students, faculty, and even external partners. In this theme, innovative education also emerged. Institutions must also allocate resources for technology and capacity development of those who participate in academic and administrative aspects in order to facilitate these strategies. Resilience has become a fundamental characteristic of the capacity in conducting remote operations, pivot to digital platforms, and consistently train staff. Empowered personnel are essential for the effective utilization of tools, rather than merely possessing them. These portray leaders as dynamic strategic thinkers and problem-solvers, who are able to rethink their plans and shift their strategies when needs arise.

The last theme articulates how crisis can change a leader's ability to lead. Leaders do not just endure crisis—they thrive among them. Three leadership styles emerged as pivotal to institutional resilience—adaptive, transformative, and collaborative. Adaptive leadership was characterized by a leader's flexibility in making quick turns and shifts based on what should be done especially when the situation calls for it. On the other hand, transformative leadership focuses on a leader's strategic foresight and compelling vision, encouraging members to grow and innovate. Additionally, collaborative leadership highlights a culture of shared responsibility, building trust within stakeholders, and fostering trust and accountability in the school community. This reveals that resilience is shaped by how a leader responds, cares, and strategizes.

All these make up a resilient leader. This framework may be a useful tool for educational leaders in institutions that are prone to educational disruptions. This may be embedded in training educational leaders in crisis preparedness and planning as it offers practical insights on how to build institutional sustainability and resilience.

EPILOGUE

Two thousand twenty – a year of vulnerabilities, uncertainties, complexities, and ambiguity. They have been there all along; yet 2020 exposed all of them. These four numbers, describing thousand counts, challenged millions – it carried with it a crisis everyone did not expect—the COVID-19 pandemic. A silent challenger; a quiet killer. It ended thousands, not limited to life, but opportunities alike.

When the world shut its doors, schools did have the opportunity to pause; as they needed to act, respond, and survive. And behind these verbs are leaders. Leaders who took the challenge head on, with hesitation. Maybe. But with dedication to thrive? Indeed.

This paper seeks how these educational leaders responded, survived, and thrived amidst crises. And there is more than the pandemic with what this study sought. More than an academic requirement, this journey was more transformative. Listening to stories of courage, loss, commitment, and compassion brought me realization that being a leader is easy in no way—the whole organization depends on one's effectiveness; therefore, taking on this challenge is already an act of bravery and service. The resilience possessed by these leaders was nothing short of inspiring. Standing still and standing tall when others gave up—a testament that nothing can beat an individual with a vision. A vision not only for the organization—but for the best interest of the people they serve. This study reopened my eyes perceiving crisis not just as an obstacle, a test—but a symbol of victory, a path for a greener pasture.

The recent health crisis may have been evidenced to be the major disruptor, however, upon discovery, there were more—natural disasters and manpower crisis were recurrent, fracturing operations of educational institutions. The results showed a number of recurring themes, which included the types of disasters these institutions have faced in the past, which are the latter mentioned; the strategies that resulted from the dynamism of educational leaders, and the resilience that became stronger shown by their leadership styles and approaches employed while facing and thriving through crises.

In the context of building resilience, dynamism increased in the face of crises—the importance of establishing crisis management structures, role of assessing and preparing for potential risks, consulting with the right

stakeholders, strengthening financial and human resources, and prioritization of investing in technology and capacity building—these were treated not just as needs, but a means to thrive.

In the face of going through crises, educational leaders learned to become resilient—they adapted and conquered. Three of the leadership styles emerged as they faced difficulties—adaptive, transformational, and collaborative. They became an inspiration to their team members, they learned to swiftly change courses according to what is needed, and they saw the beauty of collaboration and how it helps on improving decisions. Regardless of the leadership style they have executed, it all boils down to the value of resilience.

Though patterns emerged, it is notable that each response to crisis varies among each institution. This is mainly because of distinct contexts—size, geographical location, available resources, and attributes. The way educational leaders manage their unique circumstances varies with the conditions that were present. However, there was still a recurring need for every aspect—need for proactive solutions and adaptive implementation. All these implies that despite the unique challenges institutions have, the need for an educational leader who thinks strategically and responds adaptively is urgently demanded in a twenty-first century educational institution. Moreover, effective crisis management frameworks must be implemented in order to withstand, adapt, and thrive in times of difficulties.

In light of this, regulatory agencies and authorities must issue guidelines for crisis management and create standardized support systems for private higher education institutions. Institutions must also institutionalize the creation and establishment of crisis management structures, detail their roles and responsibilities, and capacitate them for better delivery of these roles. Additionally, they must regularly conduct and review their risk assessment and contingency planning to better navigate potential threats that may occur. Institutions must also strengthen their financial and human resources as these two are indispensable aspects of institutional operation. In addition to this, institutions must invest in technology to better prepare for future disruptions as this ensures the continuity of essential services in the institutions. Moreover, investment in human capital development is just as important, as they must deliver services of quality and must be prepared for future crises. Lastly, educational leaders should know the importance of collaboration and consultation with the right stakeholders as this will affect the immediate and crucial decisions to be made, especially in times of crises.

Despite having encountered crises in unique contexts, the major challenge institutions centered on how to sustain institutional operations. Though filled with different narratives, there is still more to be studied and explored in terms of how institutions build resilience in their communities.

This study extends beyond just the pandemic—it tells us that leadership matters the most in times of adversity. Reflecting on the narratives, crises, despite the waves it brings, there must be sailors who are determined, brave, and strategic. Navigating the course with purpose and resilience.

Conclusion

This study examined the experiences and practices employed by educational leaders in times of crisis. Further, this explored the challenges and approaches they utilized in facing crises such as natural disasters, the recent health crisis which is the COVID-19 pandemic, and the manpower crisis characterized by the unprecedented migration of teachers to public schools. More than being identified as crises, these became opportunities for reformation and innovation in educational institutions.

This study further explored that institutions produced strategies to cope up with the aftermath of crisis increasing dynamism. Crisis management structures were formally established and institutionalized; regular risk assessments were conducted; resources such as human and financial were secured for continuous operations, investment on human resources was evident as they will be having a major role on doing the groundwork for building institutional resilience; stakeholders were chosen for making well-informed decisions, as it helps educational leaders discern irrelevant inputs from actually substantial ones; and innovative education emerged, emphasizing the role of technology in operational continuity—it was sought that institutions that laid preparation for future crises embedded and invested in technology to remain relevant and resilient even after the pandemic.

Three leadership styles also emerged, namely adaptive, transformational, and collaborative. The crises paved the way for educational leaders to evolve. It changed their way of action and perspective. These changes were not random, rather, they are made from experiences of difficulty, challenging them to become resilient, shaping them to be more grounded, purpose-driven, and strategic. The crisis has become a catalyst of growth and innovation.

While some schools were left with no choice but to permanently cease during the COVID-19 pandemic, this study focused on how institutions managed to continue their operations despite the tremendous catastrophe that happened. These institutions effectively responded and emerged stronger as they acted with dynamism, built strategies for resilience, and evolved through the challenging times.

Building on this, it is crucial to note that not all institutions are in similar contexts. These institutions, though given the identity that they are all private higher institutions, are equipped with diverse challenges, capacities, and environments—ranging from size, locations, structures, and available resources. Though common themes may have emerged, each response was extremely influenced by their particular environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, these are the following recommendations for private higher education institutions to build institutional resilience:

For the improvement of practice, educational institutions should develop capacity building initiatives for both academic and administrative staff, which is anchored on the resilient leader framework. Training may include the

skills that they need to possess in managing crises. They must be capacitated on how to establish crisis management structures, conduct risk assessments, involve the right stakeholders, and manage resources. These will promote proactive rather than reactive solutions that will help them thrive in times of difficulty.

In terms of policy, higher authorities such as the Commission on Education and other regulatory bodies should consider crafting and implementing guidelines about Crisis Management and Response. This must set the standards for educational institutions and leaders, incorporating and institutionalizing their preparedness in the context of crisis management.

For future research, it is recommended to broaden the study and the applicability of the output—the 'resilient leader' framework—to other higher education institutions, especially public schools, or institutions with other distinct contexts such as geographic location and size. Researchers are also encouraged to investigate the long-term impacts of resilience to an institution's sustainability.

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